

Phytochemical Screening and Antibacterial Activity of Leaf and Stem Bark Extracts of *Anogeissus leiocarpa* (Marke)

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Abstract

Anogeissus leiocarpa is used in Northern Nigeria's ethnomedicine. The leaves and stem bark were investigated for its antibacterial efficacy and phytochemical attributes against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The plant parts underwent systematic processing, involving air drying, pulverization, and extraction through percolation in ethanol and aqueous solvents. Aqueous stem bark extract displayed strong saponins, moderate alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and tannin. Ethanol stem bark extract exhibited moderate saponins and a variety of phytochemicals, excluding triterpenes. Antibacterial screening using the agar well diffusion method revealed the highest zone of inhibition for ethanol stem bark (21mm at 100 mg/ml) against *S. aureus* and aqueous stem bark (20mm at 100 mg/ml) against *S. pneumoniae*, surpassing amoxicillin (10mm at 200mg/ml). Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) for *S. aureus*: aqueous leaves at 50mg/ml, ethanol leaves at 25mg/ml, aqueous stem bark at 12.5mg/ml, and ethanol stem bark at 6.25mg/ml. Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) for *S. aureus* were consistent, recorded at 50mg/ml for aqueous and ethanol leaves, and 25mg/ml for aqueous and ethanol stem bark. For *S. pneumoniae*, MBC values were observed as 50mg/ml for aqueous and ethanol leaves, 50mg/ml for aqueous stem bark, and 12.5mg/ml for ethanol stem bark. Phytochemical analysis identified common constituents, including saponins, terpenoids, flavonoids, and tannin, across all extracts. *A. leiocarpa* extracts demonstrated significant bioactive components against the tested pathogens, aligning with its traditional medicinal uses. The presence of phytochemical constituents substantiates the observed antimicrobial efficacy. Consequently, *A. leiocarpa* is a promising contender for drug development, presenting therapeutic avenues for treating diseases caused by these pathogens.

Keywords: *Anogeissus leiocarpa*, Antibacterial, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, leaves, Stem bark

1.0 Introduction

Infectious diseases represent a substantial global peril, resulting in an estimated 10,000 fatalities every day [1]. The rise of drug-resistant pathogenic microorganisms, particularly antibiotic-resistant strains, intensifies concerns about the effectiveness of current treatments [2]. The indiscriminate use of antimicrobial drugs, prevalent in the treatment of infectious diseases, contributes substantially to this resistance [3]. Moreover, pathogens such as *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas*, and members of Enterobacteriaceae have developed resistance to older antibiotics, underscoring the urgency to

develop novel antimicrobial agents effective against these pathogens.

Plants emerge as promising sources for traditional medicine and pharmaceutical drugs, given their vast potential applications. Traditional medicine remains crucial for a significant portion of the global population, addressing the scarcity and high costs associated with orthodox medicine [4,5]. Plants play a pivotal role in drug development, offering novel leads for disease treatment and prevention [6,7]. Phytochemicals, diverse compounds synthesized by plants, contribute to maintaining physiological functions and act as defense mechanisms against pathogens

such as bacteria, fungi, insects, and animals. Bioactive plant compounds serve as templates for synthetic drugs and precursors, facilitating the production of semi-synthetic drugs [6]. The urgency to screen plants for pharmaceuticals intensifies with rapid deforestation and the concurrent loss of biodiversity worldwide [8]. The vital role of herbs in managing human ailments cannot be overstated.

Anogeissus leiocarpa, widely utilized in Northern Nigeria's ethnomedicine, belongs to the family Combretaceae and is recognized by various names across regions. This graceful tropical tree, with occurrences ranging from Senegal to Sudan and Ethiopia in Africa, holds significance in traditional medicine for treating diverse ailments. The decoction and maceration of its stem bark address conditions such as anorexia, constipation, malaria, jaundice, fatigue, itching, eczema, psoriasis, carbuncles, wounds, and various diseases, including helminthiasis, schistosomiasis, leprosy, amoebic dysentery, trypanosomiasis, tuberculosis, and sexually transmitted infections [9]. Research underscores *A. leiocarpus*'s pharmacological activities, including strong antibacterial and antifungal properties against pathogenic microorganisms [10,11,12].

However, despite its ethnopharmacological significance, a comprehensive investigation into the antibacterial effectiveness and phytochemical attributes of *A. leiocarpus* against clinical pathogenic bacterial isolates such as *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*, remains lacking. This study aims to fill this research gap by systematically exploring the antimicrobial potential of *A. leiocarpus* extracts, specifically targeting clinical isolates, namely *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The statement of the problem emphasizes the critical need for alternative treatments in the face of escalating infectious diseases and antibiotic resistance. The aim is to enhance our understanding of *A. leiocarpus*'s therapeutic potential, and the objectives include determining phytochemical constituents, evaluating its antibacterial efficacy, and determining the minimum inhibitory concentration and minimum bactericidal concentration on the bacterial isolates. This research contributes to the development of effective antimicrobial agents to address diseases caused by these pathogens and offers insights into harnessing the therapeutic potential of *A. leiocarpus*.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 Study Area

This study was carried out in Federal University Gusau, Microbiology Laboratory. The sample *Anogeissus leiocarpus* plants part extract was obtained at the back of Faculty of Science, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara state.

2.2 Plant sample collection

The plant sample used in this research was the stem bark and leaves of *A. leiocarpus* which was obtained at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State. The leaves of *A. leiocarpus* are simple, alternate, and elliptical in shape. They are usually about 6 to 12 centimeters long and 3 to 6 centimeters wide. The leaves have a glossy green color. The bark of the tree is distinctive, often smooth and greyish-white. As the tree matures, the bark may become rougher and darker. These parts of the plant were collected inside sterile polythene bags and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at Federal University Gusau for further analysis.

2.3 Preparation of plant materials

The fresh leaves and stem bark were properly washed with tap water, and rinsed with distilled water. The leaves and stem bark were air-dried at room temperature for 2 weeks and pulverized to a fine powder of 60 mesh size using a clean wooden mortar and pestle.

2.3.1 Preparation of plant extract

This was done as described by Ahmad et al. [13]. The plant parts of *A. leiocarpus* were prepared by percolation in ethanol and aqueous. 25g of each of the pulverized plant parts were separately soaked in 250ml of ethanol and aqueous, it was allowed to stand for 72 hours with intermittent stirring. Each preparation of the leaf and stem bark of *A. leiocarpus* was decanted and filtered through a muslin cloth. The filtrates obtained were evaporated to dryness using a water bath and stored in a sterile plastic container protected from sunlight until required for analysis. The prepared powder was used for the phytochemical and antibacterial analysis.

2.4 Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical screening was carried out at Microbiology Laboratory in Federal University Gusau. The screening was conducted on different extract to ascertain the presence of bioactive components in the leaves and stem bark of *A. leiocarpus*. The presence of alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, steroids, tannins, resins, terpenoid, triterpene, saponins and flavonoids were determined using the procedure describe by Mann et al. [14] and Kaboré et al. [15].

2.5 Phytochemical analysis of *A. leiocarpus* leaves and stem bark

2.5.1 Test for Flavonoids

Three (3g) of the plant extract was added to 1ml of 10% sodium hydroxide, and was thoroughly shaken. Intense yellow coloration indicate the presence of flavonoids [16].

2.5.2 Test for Tannin (Ferric Chloride Test)

One (1g) of the plant extract was dissolves in 10cm³ of distilled water then filtered. Two drops of ferric chloride solution was added to the filtrate. Formation of blue-black precipitation observed indicates the presence of hydrolysable tannins and green precipitate indicates the presence of condensed tannins. [17].

2.5.3 Test for Alkaloids (Mayer's test)

Two drops of Mayer's reagent was added to 5cm³ of the plant extract and the solution was been shake vigorously in a test tube. A cream colored precipitate indicates the presence of Alkaloids [17].

2.5.4 Test for Glycosides

Five (5g) of 50% of hydrogen sulphide was added to the extracts in a test tube. The mixture was then boiled in a water bath for 15minutes. It was allowed to cool and neutralized with 10% sodium chloride, 5ml of Fehling solution was added and the mixture was boiled for 5minutes. A brick red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides [16].

2.5.5 Test for Saponins

Two (2g) of the powdered sample was boiled in 20cm³ distilled water in a water bath and filtered. 10cm³ of the filtrate was mixed with 5cm³ of distilled water and shake vigorously for a stable persistent froth. The frothing was then mixed with 3 drops of olive oil and shake vigorously, the formation of emulsion was observed [17].

2.5.6 Test for Steroids

This was carried out according to the method of Harbone [16]. 0.5g of the extract was dissolved in 2ml of chlorofoam, 2ml of sulfuric acid was carefully added to form lower layer, and a reddish-brown color at the interface indicate the presence of a steroid.

2.6 Determination of Microbiological properties.

2.6.1 Media preparation

All media used during this research work were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions (Nutrient agar, Muller Hinton agar and Nutrient broth) were weighed as instructed by the manufacturer poured in a conical flask containing sterile distilled water, boil to dissolve and autoclave at 121°C for 24hours. It was allowed to cool, poured into sterile petri dishes and were allowed to solidify.

2.6.2 Clinical sample collection

Two (2) Clinical isolates from sputum samples were collected using an agar slant from medical laboratory of Ahmad Sani Yarima Bakura Specialist Hospital Gusau, Zamfara state. It was transported to Microbiology Laboratory in the Department of Microbiology, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, the organisms include: *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The organisms were sub-cultured and stored on nutrient agar slant for characterization and identification.

2.7 Characterization and Identification of the Isolates

The isolates were characterized morphologically and biochemically. Gram staining, Catalase, Citrate, Methyl Red, Urease, Indole and Motility test were performed as carried out by Okoye and

Onuorah [18]. The isolates were identified with the scheme of Krieg and Holt [19].

2.8 Antimicrobial Screening of the Isolates

2.8.1 Preparation of Different Concentrations of the Extracts

Four different concentration of the extracts used were 25mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 75mg/ml and 3100mg/ml. These was done by measuring appropriate grams of the extracts and dissolved into dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO).

2.8.2 Control Experiment Using Antibiotics

The control experiment was carried out to compare the diameter zone of inhibition from the extracts and already standardized antibiotics. This will enable further prescription of either plants or antibiotics with antimicrobial activities. The antibiotic used was amoxicillin.

2.8.3 Agar well diffusion method

The agar well diffusion method was used to determine the antibacterial activity of the plant extracts. Suspension of the bacterial isolates was made in sterile normal saline and adjusted to 0.5 McFarland Standard. Mueller Hinton agar plates were uniformly seeded by means of sterile swab dipped into the suspension and streaked on the agar plate surface on the Mueller Hinton agar and allow to set then labelled. A sterile cork borer 5mm was used to punch holes and was filled with different concentrations of the extract which was labelled accordingly; 25mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 75mg/ml and 100mg/ml and the control antibiotics used was amoxicillin. They were left on the bench for 1hour for adequate diffusion of the extracts and incubated at 37°C for 48hours. After incubation, the zone of inhibition around each well was measured using a meter rule [20].

2.8.4 Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration of the extracts was determined by using the broth dilution technique [21]. The MIC helps to measure the concentration of an antibiotic necessary to inhibit growth of standardized inoculums under defined conditions [22]. Two fold serial dilutions of the extract in liquid medium was prepared to achieve different

concentration of 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25 and 3.125mg/ml. The Isolates was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard using a syringe, 0.2 ml of the standardized test bacterial suspension was added to each of the test tube. All inoculated tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 24hours, at the end of 24hours. The minimum concentration of the extracts that showed no growth was taken as MIC of the extracts against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and were documented [12].

2.8.5 Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was carried out to determine whether the test microbes were killed or only their growth was inhibited. Nutrient agar was prepared, sterilized at 121°C for 15min poured into sterile Petri dish and was allowed to cool and solidify. The content of the MIC in the serial dilution was then sub-cultured onto the prepared medium, incubation was made at 37°C for 24hours after which the plate of the medium was observed for colony growth, the MBC were the isolate without colony growth [20].

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Microbiological parameters

The identification of the isolates *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was established through a thorough examination of their biochemical profiles and gram staining characteristics (Table 1).

Table 1: Morphological and Biochemical characteristics of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* Isolates.

Test	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
Gram staining	+ cocci	+cocci
Catalase	+	-
Citrate	+	-
Methyl Red	+	-
Urease	+	-
Indole	-	-
Motility	-	-

Keys: + = positive; - = negative

3.2 Phytochemical Screening

Medicinal plants have been used for centuries in various cultures as traditional remedies for a wide range of health conditions. These plants contain bioactive compounds that can have therapeutic effects on the human body. They serve as potent therapeutic agents, offering a natural and holistic approach to health and well-being. Rich in bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolics, these plants exert a myriad of pharmacological effects. From their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that combat oxidative stress and cellular damage to their antimicrobial actions against pathogens, medicinal plants play a crucial role in preventing and alleviating various health conditions. Additionally, their analgesic, immunomodulatory, and neuroprotective benefits contribute to a wide range of therapeutic applications. Whether addressing cardiovascular health, supporting the immune system, or aiding in wound healing, these plants offer diverse therapeutic potentials.

The phytochemical screening of *Anogeissus leiocarpa* extracts, using both aqueous and ethanol solvents, aimed to identify various bioactive compounds. The analysis included the presence or absence of flavonoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, alkaloids, triterpenes, resins, terpenoids, steroids, and phenolic compounds.

In the aqueous stem bark extract, the screening revealed the presence of saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, terpenoids, resins, triterpenes, and phenolic compounds. Notably, steroids were absent in this extract. This is similar to the finding of Wadood et al. [23], who carried out a phytochemical analysis on medicinal plants and reported the presence of these phytochemical constituent's. In contrast, the aqueous leaf extract exhibited the presence of saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, and terpenoids, while resins and steroids were not detected.

The ethanol stem bark extract exhibited a diverse array of identified compounds, including tannins, steroids, flavonoid, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, resins, terpenoids, and phenolic compounds. However, triterpenes were notably absent in this extract. This is in agreement with the findings of Mann [24] who studied antimicrobial activity of *A. leiocarpa* and *T. avicennioides* against infectious diseases prevalent in Nigerian hospital and reported that

the result of the phytochemical analysis of the stem bark extracts of *A. leiocarpa* indicated presence of tannins, saponins, phenols, steroids and anthraquinones. Also, in accordance with the report of Namadina [25] who state that the phytochemical analysis of the stem-bark extracts revealed the presence of some secondary metabolites such as carbohydrate, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, saponins, steroid/triterpenes and absences of anthraquinones. The information on the presence or absence and the type of phytochemical constituents especially the secondary metabolites are useful taxonomic keys in identifying a particular species and distinguishing it from a related species, thus helping in the delimitation of taxa [26].

On the other hand, the ethanol leaf extract showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, resins, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, and tannins, while glycosides and triterpenes were absent (Table 2). This is similar to the finding of Kawo et al. [27] who screened the leaf using aqueous and ethanol as the extract and reported that only alkaloids were absent.

The results of the phytochemical screening of the plant extract revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, which is similar to the studies conducted by Mann et al. [14], Kaboré et al. [15] and Aliyu and Sani, [28]. Alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, steroids, tannins, anthraquinones, saponins, and flavonoids were identified in the study by Mann et al. [14] and Kaboré et al. [15]. Similarly, the investigation conducted by Aliyu and Sani [28] reported the presence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, and glycosides in both ethanol and aqueous stem bark extracts of *Anogeissus leiocarpa*.

Saponins, are recognized for their surfactant properties, exhibiting antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities. This suggests their potential contribution to managing microbial infections and inflammation. The presence of alkaloids in *A. leiocarpa* encompasses pharmacological activities such as analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, positioning the plant as a natural source for addressing pain and inflammation [29]. Rich in flavonoids, the plant presents antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties, showcasing its potential as a source of bioactive compounds with health-

promoting effects. Glycosides are important phytochemicals which are used as antibacterial agents [30]. Glycosides identified in *A. leiocarpus* may offer various biological activities, including cardiovascular benefits and anti-inflammatory effects, supporting its potential in addressing cardiovascular health and inflammation-related conditions. Tannins, are known for their antioxidant and therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities, which underscore the plant's potential as a source of natural compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits. The presence of tannins suggest the growth inhibitory effect of plant extracts on bacteria [31]. Terpenoids found in *A. leiocarpus* contribute to its pharmacological activities, including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties, highlighting its value as a source of bioactive compounds. Resins and triterpenes may exhibit antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects,

aligning with traditional medicinal uses for addressing microbial infections and inflammatory conditions. The presence of phenolic compounds in *A. leiocarpus* emphasizes its potential health-promoting effects through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities.

This comprehensive phytochemical analysis provides valuable insights into the bioactive constituents present in different extracts of *A. leiocarpus*. The variations observed in the composition of compounds across the extracts highlight the importance of solvent selection in extracting specific phytochemicals. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the plant's potential pharmacological activities, offering a basis for further exploration into the therapeutic properties of this plant.

Table 2: Phytochemical Analysis of Aqueous and Ethanolic Extract of *Anogeissus leiocarpa* leaf and stem bark

Phytochemical components	Aqueous stem bark	Aqueous leaves	Ethanol stem bark	Ethanol leaves
Alkaloid	++	+	+	+
Saponins	+++	++	++	+
Glycosides	+	+	+	-
Resins	+	-	+	+
Flavonoid	++	+	+	+
Terpenoid	++	++	+	+
Steroid	-	-	+	+
Tannin	++	++	+	++
Triterpenes	+	+	-	-
Phenolic compound	+	+	+	+

Keys: - = Absent; += Low concentration; ++ = Moderate concentration; +++ = Highly concentration

3.3 Zone of Inhibition

The assessment of the zone of inhibition for varying concentrations of the extracts and the control against the isolates demonstrated significant antibacterial efficacy of the extracts (Table 3). The ethanol stem bark extract exhibited the highest zone of inhibition, measuring 21mm at 100mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 19mm at 100mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*. The exceptional inhibitory efficacy of the ethanol stem bark extract, indicates its substantial impact on microbial growth. In comparison, the ethanol leaves extract displayed a maximum zone of inhibition of 17mm at 100mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 15mm at 100mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*.

The aqueous stem bark extract demonstrated a higher zone of inhibition, of 19mm at 100 mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 20mm at 100mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*. Similarly, the aqueous leaves extract showed the highest concentration of 16mm at 100mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 17mm at 100mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*.

As a control measure, amoxicillin exhibited a zone of inhibition of 15mm at 200mg/ml and 10mm at 200mg/ml against *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*, respectively. These findings collectively emphasize the significant antibacterial activity of the *Anogeissus leiocarpa* extracts against the tested microbial strains, with the ethanol stem bark extract exhibiting

remarkable inhibitory effects. The zones of inhibition of the standardized antibiotics, the plant show remarkable antibacterial activity to the antibiotics. This aligns with the findings of Mann et al. [32], Elsidning et al. [33], and Timothy et al. [2], who reported the potential effectiveness of *Anogeissus leiocarpa* against various pathogenic microorganisms, including *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella* spp., *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The susceptibility of the test organisms to the plant extracts was evident in the zones of inhibition produced, with variations observed among different organisms and across distinct plant part extracts.

According to Prescott [34], the effectiveness of an agent can vary depending on the target species. The variability in the zones of inhibition supports this notion, emphasizing the nuanced impact of the plant extracts on different bacterial species and across various plant parts. This outcome is consistent with the collective evidence from various studies, suggesting that certain medicinal plants, including *Anogeissus leiocarpa*, hold promise as potential sources of novel antibacterial agents [35].

Table 3: Zone of inhibition of the extracts concentration and control against the isolates (mm)

Test organism	Concentration Mg/ml	Aqueous leaves	Ethanol leaves	Aqueous stem bark	Ethanol stem Bark	Control 200 mg/ml
<i>S. aureus</i>	25	10	10	13	16	15
	50	13	11	14	17	
	75	15	14	16	19	
	100	16	17	19	21	
<i>S. Pneumoniae</i>	25	11	10	16	16	10
	50	13	12	17	18	
	75	14	14	19	18	
	100	17	15	20	21	

3.4 Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) serves as a crucial indicator of a substance's effectiveness against a particular pathogen. The MIC and MBC assay procedures are frequently used to evaluate some diverse agents such as antibiotics, antiseptics, disinfectants and chemotherapeutic agents [36].

In the determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), the aqueous leaf extract exhibited a higher MIC of 50mg/ml for both *S. aureus* and *S. pneumonia* (Table 4). This higher MIC suggests a comparatively lower potency of this particular extract in inhibiting bacterial growth. Conversely, the ethanolic leaves extract displayed a lower MIC of 25mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 12.5mg/ml for *S. pneumonia*, indicating a more potent inhibitory effect.

The MIC values of 6.25mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 12.5mg/ml for *S. pneumonia* in the aqueous stem bark extract suggest a relatively higher efficacy against these bacterial strains. Meanwhile, the ethanolic stem bark extract

exhibited an MIC of 12.5mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 6.25mg/ml for *S. pneumonia*, indicating a comparable inhibitory effect. This is in agreement with low MIC range of 5-20 mg/mL reported by Ali et al. [20].

The variations in Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) observed in this study, can be attributed to several factors influencing the antimicrobial efficacy of *A. leiocarpus* extracts. The distinct MIC values for different extracts and bacterial strains underscore the complexity of the interactions between the plant compounds and the target microorganisms.

These discrepancies in MIC values from previous studies, such as those reported by Mann et al. [24] and Timothy et al. [2], which ranged from 5-20 mg/ml, highlight the inherent variability in antimicrobial activity attributed to factors like geographic location, extraction methods, and variations in plant material.

Notably, the notably higher MIC of 90 mg/ml reported by Umar and Mohammad [37] for the ethanol extract against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* emphasizes the need for context-

specific evaluation of plant extracts, as different studies may yield diverse results due to inherent

variations in methodologies and conditions.

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of the leaves and Stem bark extract on the isolates

Test organism	Concentration Mg/ml	Aqueous Leaves	Ethanol Leaves	Aqueous Stem bark	Ethanol Stem bark
<i>S. aureus</i>	50	Ox	-	-	-
	25	+	ox	-	-
	12.5	+	+	+	ox
	6.25	+	+	ox	+
	3.125	+	+	+	+
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	50	Ox	-	-	-
	25	+	+	-	-
	12.5	+	ox	ox	-
	6.25	+	+	+	ox
	3.125	+	+	+	+

Keys: - = No growth; ox = MIC; + = growth

3.5 Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) reveals the lowest concentration at which the antimicrobial agent not only hinders microbial growth but also completely eliminates the microorganisms. They are important in evaluating the bactericidal potential of a substance and facilitating the development of targeted and potent antimicrobial strategies. The combined insights derived from MIC and MBC assessments play a significant role in optimizing antimicrobial therapies, ensuring drug efficacy, and fostering judicious utilization in the battle against infectious diseases. The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) findings in this study revealed distinctive values for the various extracts against *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*. The aqueous leaves extract exhibited a higher MBC of 50mg/ml for both bacterial strains. Similarly, the ethanolic leaves extract displayed an MBC of 50mg/ml against both *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*. The aqueous and ethanol extracts of *A. leiocarpus* leaves indicated significant bactericidal activities against the tested clinical isolates. This is in conjunction with the finding of

Namadina, et al. [31] who studied phytochemical constituents and antibacterial activities of *A. leiocarpus* stem and reported that the methanolic extract of *A. leiocarpus* stem on the isolates showed considerable bactericidal effects.

Contrastingly, the aqueous stem bark extract demonstrated an MBC of 25mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 50mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*. In the case of the ethanolic stem bark extract, the MBC values were 25mg/ml for *S. aureus* and 12.5mg/ml for *S. pneumoniae*. There were variation in the cidal effect of the two extract. These showed that the pathogens were most killed at 50mg/ml. These findings is in conformity with the report of Ali et al.[20] where the pathogens were most killed at 40mg/ml. These MBC values provide insights into the concentration of the extracts required to exert bactericidal effects on the tested microorganisms. The varying MBC values among different extracts and bacterial strains underscore the nuanced antimicrobial potential of *A. leiocarpus* and emphasize the need for a comprehensive understanding of the distinct effects exhibited by each extract against specific pathogens.

Table 5: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of the leaves and Stem bark extract against the isolates

Test organism	Concentration Mg/ml	Aqueous Leaves	Ethanol Leaves	Aqueous Stem bark	Ethanol Stem bark
<i>S. aureus</i>	50	Ox	ox	-	-
	25	+	+	ox	ox
	12.5	+	+	+	+
	6.25	+	+	+	+
	3.125	+	+	+	+
<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	50	ox	ox	ox	-
	25	+	+	+	-
	12.5	+	+	+	ox
	6.25	+	+	+	+

3.125	+	+	+	+
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5.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, this investigation delving into the antibacterial effectiveness and phytochemical attributes of *A. leiocarpus* (Marke) extracts against clinical pathogenic bacterial isolates has yielded significant findings. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, steroids, tannins, anthraquinones, saponins, and flavonoids. This aligns with previous studies affirming the plant's pharmacological potential.

The zones of inhibition observed in the antibacterial assay demonstrated the remarkable antibacterial activity of the extracts against *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*. The varying concentrations of the extracts exhibited differential inhibitory effects, with the ethanol stem bark extract displaying particularly noteworthy inhibitory effects.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values were determined, showcasing the concentration range at which the extracts effectively inhibited bacterial growth. The findings indicated distinct MIC values for different extracts against both bacterial strains, emphasizing the importance of considering the specific extract and bacterial species in antimicrobial studies.

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) values further elucidated the concentration required for bactericidal effects, highlighting the potential of *Anogeissus leiocarpa* extracts to not only inhibit but also eradicate pathogenic bacteria.

6.0 Recommendation

Based on the results obtained, it is recommended that further studies be conducted to explore the specific mechanisms underlying the antibacterial activity of *A. leiocarpus* extracts. Investigating the potential synergistic effects of combining different extracts or assessing the extracts in combination with conventional antibiotics could provide valuable insights into enhanced antibacterial efficacy.

Moreover, studies focusing on the safety profile and potential side effects of the extracts are crucial for assessing their suitability for therapeutic use. Exploring the extracts' impact on other clinically relevant bacteria and conducting in vivo studies would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of their antimicrobial potential.

The findings from this research suggest that *Anogeissus leiocarpa* holds promise as a potential source of antibacterial agents. Further exploration and development of these extracts could pave the way for the formulation of novel antimicrobial drugs, contributing to the ongoing efforts to combat bacterial infections and antibiotic resistance.

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8.0 Conflicts of Interest

The authors assert their absence of any conflict of interest. This manuscript has not been previously published or presented, either in part or in its entirety, and is not currently under review by another journal. The authors have familiarized themselves with the journal's policies, and they affirm that the manuscript and the study adhere to these guidelines. Both authors have actively participated in substantial work that has led to the creation of this manuscript, and they collectively and individually take responsibility for its content. All co-authors have reached an agreement to submit the manuscript.

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